

The Invention History of Multi-Chip Integrated Silicon Photonics

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I dislike rehashing old ideas and prefer creating new ones. Therefore, I don't teach at universities. University teaching involves imparting existing knowledge to students. To uphold the spirit of public service and remain independent of investors influence, self-funding my scientific research has been a journey of immense hardship. Furthermore, I did everything myself to save spending. I previously relied on technical consulting, web design, graphic design, and writing poetry for clients. These tasks corresponded to the fields of technology, art, and literature. I viewed these services as consistent with my public welfare philosophy. However, since the emergence of AI, these sources of income have vanished. Although I believe the tasks completed by AI are not yet perfect, they are sufficient and cost-effective for most clients.

My current focus is on my two major new inventions: distributed AI robot series and pixelated modular architectural systems. However, seeing that companies are still vying for silicon photonics patents, it's necessary to mention them again.

During the nineties, I majored in semiconductor engineering. The field of electrical and electronic engineering is very broad. At that time, many of my classmates, even those who did not major in the field, joined the cleanrooms after graduation and were able to pay for a house in Taipei in full after only three years. However, I did not follow that path. Because of my personality, I knew as soon as I saw the cleanroom working environment that this kind of work was not suitable for me. I indirectly learned all my practical experience in the process by asking experienced people around.

Looking back now, if I did the work of semiconductor fabricated process, I would have become proficient in the practical experience of semiconductor engineering and manufacturing. And then, I would have been firmly confined by the mindset of semiconductor manufacturing processes. It would have been impossible for me to later invent the multi-chip integrated silicon photonics architecture, which was considered a pipe dream at the time, in 1999 after graduating from graduate school.

It began simply because silica processes were very difficult to locate at the time while silicon processes were flourishing, which prompted my shift to silicon semiconductors. Since I was an obscure engineer back then, I did not feel confident seeking collaboration with only a WDM or a modulator, so I developed a complete multi-chip

integrated silicon photonics architecture instead. I started preparing presentations for potential partners in 2004, but a detour occurred. During my regular paper study, I saw Intel's silicon photonics based on silicon light-emitting technology published in Nature. I quickly wrote a manuscript and submitted it to point out that the silicon light-emitting route was mistaken. After it was rejected, I chose to make the information public and let history decide who was correct.

Figure serves as computer screenshot evidence. The first problem to solve was the coupling loss between the photonic chip and the optical fiber in the multi-chip integrated architecture. The significant optical coupling loss was the biggest problem with this architecture, and the main reason why it was considered unfeasible at the time. File 1 is the optical simulation of the Antiguided wave, Lossy_Antiguided_Simulation, dated 1999. This was the optical simulation conducted to solve the coupling problem between silicon chips and optical fibers. I later applied for patent TWI443395 for this. File 2 is the presentation file Invention v1, dated 2004. The reason it was named Invention v1 is that silicon photonics was my first invention in life. It ultimately became widely known, and subsequently, no one cared who the original creator was. As for the multi-chip integrated silicon photonics architecture, since it had been made public, a patent could not be applied for. I applied for US patents US8406579, US8478091, and US8594474 for other key components developed for the silicon photonics system.

Figure: Computer screenshot evidence of the multi-chip integrated silicon photonics architecture

At that time, the concept of multi-chip packaging silicon photonics was ridiculed as the

ignorant talk of an amateur. Furthermore, if my submission to Nature had not been rejected in 2004, I would not have made the multi-chip integrated Silicon Photonics architecture public. By doing so, I turned it into a public good. This event also led me to move away from mainstream values and embark on a life dedicated to self-funded creation for the public interest.

The architecture utilized in Silicon Photonics research today remains essentially the same as the architecture I disclosed over twenty years ago. If this technology were the exclusive patent of a major tech giant, it is highly unlikely that Silicon Photonics would be flourishing as it is today.

When I named it OEIC, the core concept was that light sources are used as the power supply for the IC. At the time, I recognized that since standard electronic ICs rely on external power, and photonic ICs are even more complex, it was impossible for them to emit their own light. Integrating photonic and electronic chips into a single package was the only solution. Intel coined the term Silicon Photonics because their work centered on silicon light emission. However, the technology now known as CPO is fundamentally OEIC. I funded my own research, spending all my savings and the prime of my youth, and then shared it with the world for free. At the time, I was mocked and even marginalized. Today, the entire silicon photonics ecosystem is developing CPO architectures and profiting immensely from skyrocketing stock prices.

Whether it is Wikipedia or the Nobel Prize, the focus is always on mainstream academic recognition. Consider this fact: during the years when I proposed the silicon photonics architecture for multiple chip integration, I was dismissed as an amateur. How could the academic community possibly recognize me? In the days of floppy disks and CDs, many files were damaged. Fortunately, the critical evidence remains intact. Otherwise, I would never be able to clear my name.

Although funding is currently scarce, my creative work for the common good has never ceased. The experiences of Nicolaus Copernicus, Galileo Galilei, and Nikola Tesla demonstrate that truth often stands in opposition to mainstream values. People challenge my resolve, wondering why I remain so steadfast when the world shows no gratitude. Yet, I believe the majority of mankind is inherently good, and it is wrong to generalize. They are simply clouded by the prejudices of the times. I just follow in the footsteps of these predecessors, moving forward alone with courage. I do not seek personal recognition, and I do not expect a Nobel Prize. It is enough to have contributed to the world, and I have no regrets.

